

Intelligent Algorithms for Evaluating Economic Indicators Based on Machine Learning Models

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Abstract. This study focuses on the development of intelligent algorithms for evaluating economic indicators based on artificial intelligence models. In particular, the research addresses the intellectual assessment of the balance between supply and demand in sales, considered as key economic indicators. The process of predicting delays in product sales, viewed as an imbalance between supply and demand, is thoroughly examined. To this end, the problem is formulated as a classification task, and solutions are proposed using machine learning models of artificial intelligence. Specifically, intelligent algorithms based on logistic regression, decision trees, and the K-Nearest Neighbors (K-NN) methods have been developed for evaluating economic indicators. Experimental results demonstrating the effectiveness of the proposed approaches are presented.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, classification problem, economic indicators, machine learning, logistic regression, decision tree, K-NN.

I. Introduction

The rapid advancement of artificial intelligence mechanisms is significantly enhancing the processes of forecasting socio-economic indicators. Across the world, digital technologies and artificial intelligence systems are developing at a remarkable pace and are being actively integrated into various sectors, particularly into socio-economic fields. This integration focuses primarily on automating processes in economics, the social sector, public administration, and security systems through the application of digital technologies and artificial intelligence. It also involves the intellectualization of information analysis within automated control systems and the development of methods and algorithms for evaluating economic indicators.

Currently, the development of new intelligent algorithms based on the enhancement of machine learning models in artificial intelligence is progressing rapidly. Machine learning models are designed to generate statistical rules based on both structured and unstructured data. In this study, the issue of the

intellectual assessment of the balance between supply and demand in sales — recognized as key economic indicators — has been explored. Intelligent algorithms for evaluating economic indicators have been developed based on logistic regression, decision tree, and K-Nearest Neighbors (K-NN) machine learning methods, and experimental results have been obtained.

II. Development of Intelligent Algorithms for Analyzing Economic Indicators Based on Machine Learning Models

The process of intellectually assessing the balance between supply and demand in sales has been carried out as a key economic indicator. In this study, the evaluation of the balance between supply and demand has been approached through the early detection of delays in product sales. The problem of predicting such delays has been formulated as a classification task and solved using machine learning models of artificial intelligence.

Initially, a dataset was created for the machine learning models, incorporating the following features:

ID – Product identifier

B_date – Order date

P_type – Product type

P_volume – Product volume

P_stock – Quantity of the product in the warehouse

Status – Delay status in product sales

Based on the above features, a dataset for machine learning was developed and processed through the following steps:

1. **Data Collection:** Gathering raw data;
2. **Feature Selection:** Calculating correlations using Pearson and Kendall methods to select relevant features;
3. **Data Cleaning:** Identifying duplicate records and retaining the necessary ones, standardizing incorrectly formatted values, and imputing missing values (NaN) using regression techniques;
4. **Data Normalization:** Scaling values to the [0,1] range;
5. **Data Encoding:** Converting textual data into numerical form;
6. **Data Splitting:** Dividing the dataset into training and testing subsets.

After the data preprocessing was completed, algorithms based on logistic regression, decision tree, and K-Nearest Neighbors (K-NN) methods were developed.

Logistic regression is one of the statistical techniques commonly used to solve classification and regression problems [1,2]. This model predicts the probability of a dependent variable based on one or more independent variables from the dataset. Logistic regression is considered effective for making decisions related to the identification of economic indicators [2,3,5]. In this context, data concerning the factors contributing to sales delays were collected and prepared as economic indicators. These features were used as independent variables in the model.

During the development of the logistic regression-based algorithm, coefficients (gamma values) were determined from the training dataset, which represent the influence of each independent

variable on the dependent variable. Once the model was trained, new data could be input, and the probability of sales delays could be predicted accordingly. Thus, logistic regression in machine learning serves as an effective tool for forecasting economic indicators by modeling probabilities and improving classification through consideration of multiple influencing factors.

The mathematical model of the logistic regression method in machine learning can be generalized as follows:

$$p(X) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}} \quad (1)$$

Here, T represents the linear combination of the input features and is expressed through equation (2).

$$T = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 X_1 + \gamma_2 X_2 + \dots + \gamma_n X_n \quad (2)$$

here, the $\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \dots, \gamma_n$ coefficients correspond to each X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n feature.

The output $p(X)$ represents the predicted probability $Y = 1$ of the dependent variable, taking into account the input features X . In the classification of economic indicators, specifically in predicting sales delays, if $p(X) > 0,5$ occurs, the model predicts class 1; otherwise, it predicts class 0. The coefficients are defined as the ratio of the probability of an event occurring to the probability of it not occurring, and this relationship is expressed by equation (3):

$$Odds = \frac{p(X)}{1 - p(X)} \quad (3)$$

The **Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE)** method is used to evaluate the (γ) coefficients in the logistic regression model of machine learning. The likelihood function of logistic regression is defined as follows in equation (4):

$$L(\gamma) = \prod_{i=1}^n p(x_i)^{y_i} (1 - p(x_i))^{(1-y_i)} \quad (4)$$

here, y_i represents the actual binary classification outcomes (0 or 1). The goal is to find the

coefficients that maximize this likelihood function [2,4]. In this method, the loss function is commonly used to assess how well the model predicts probabilities, and it is expressed as follows in equation (5):

$$L(\gamma) = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i \log(p(x_i)) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - p(x_i))] \quad (5)$$

Step 1: Initialization;

Step 2: Data Preparation;

Step 3: Splitting the data into training and testing sets; $X_{test} \cup X_{o'quv} \in X$

Step 4: Calculate

$$T = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 X_1 + \gamma_2 X_2 + \dots + \gamma_n X_n;$$

Step 5: Determine the probability

$$p(X) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}};$$

Step 6: Estimate the coefficients

$$L(\gamma) = \prod_{i=1}^n p(x_i)^{y_i} (1 - p(x_i))^{(1-y_i)};$$

Step 7: Compute the loss function

$$L(\gamma) = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i \log(p(x_i)) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - p(x_i))];$$

Step 8: Accept new data;

Step 9: If the probability is greater than 0.5, classify as $Y=1$ otherwise, predict the $Y=0$ class;

Step 10: End.

Developing an Algorithm Based on the Decision Tree Method to Assist in Decision-Making for Identifying Sales Delays as Economic Indicators

The decision tree model in machine learning is widely used in the fields of machine learning and artificial intelligence and is one of the most effective methods for the intellectual analysis of economic indicators. In this research, an algorithm based on the decision tree method was developed to assist in decision-making for identifying sales delays as economic indicators. The decision tree in machine learning is primarily composed of nodes and leaves [6,8]. Each internal node in the decision tree makes a decision based on a particular feature. Intellectual analysis of economic indicators using machine learning's decision tree method is performed based on

the feature data of sales delays. The leaves represent the final outcome [7,10]. That is, they define whether a delay exists and its severity. In constructing a decision tree for machine learning, various criteria are used for splitting the data, and the following are some of the criteria that can be listed:

Gini Impurity. This criterion measures the accuracy of the data set and is expressed as follows [9,11]:

$$Gini(D) = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n p_i^2 \quad (6)$$

Entropy. This criterion measures the uncertainty of the data and is expressed as follows [12]:

$$Entropy(D) = -\sum_{i=1}^n p_i \log_2(p_i) \quad (7)$$

The decision tree in machine learning is trained based on the existing data set, where at each node, the best features are selected, and the data is divided according to those features. In the next step, new data is input, and the tree is traversed to determine the outcome. An algorithm based on the decision tree method has been developed to assist in decision-making for identifying sales delays as economic indicators, and it is executed in the following steps:

Step 1: Start;

Step 2: Prepare the data;

Step 3: Split the data into test and training sets $X_{test} \cup X_{o'quv} \in X, Y_{test} \cup Y_{o'quv} \in Y;$

Step 4: Train the model based on the data;

Step 5: Calculate the loss function

$$L(\gamma) = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i \log(p(x_i)) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - p(x_i))];$$

Step 6: Compute the confusion matrix;

Step 7: Evaluate the model's accuracy;

Step 8: Accept new data;

Step 9: Make predictions based on the decision tree;

Step 10: End.

Developing an Algorithm Based on the K-NN Model to Assist in Decision-Making for Identifying Sales Delays as Economic Indicators.

In this research, the K-Nearest Neighbors (K-

NN) method is one of the effective tools for intellectual analysis of economic indicators, such as identifying sales delays. In the K-NN algorithm, distance measures play an important role as they define the similarity between each data point. The following commonly used distance measures were analyzed [11,13].

Euclidean Distance: The Euclidean distance measure is one of the most commonly used distance metrics and is expressed as follows.

$$d = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - y_i)^2} \quad (8)$$

here x_i and y_i represent the coordinates of two points in an n - dimensional space.

Manhattan Distance: The Manhattan distance, also known as the L1 distance, is defined as follows.

$$d = \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i - y_i| \quad (9)$$

Minkowski Distance: This distance measure is a generalization of both the Euclidean and Manhattan distances, and it is defined as follows (10).

$$d = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n |x_i - y_i|^p \right)^{1/p} \quad (10)$$

In the formula above, the parameter p defines the order of the norm. An algorithm based on the K-NN method to assist in decision-making for detecting delays in sales as economic indicators was developed, and it is implemented through the following steps:

Step 1: Start.

Step 2: A dataset $S = \{(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n)\}$ is created, where x_i represents feature vectors, and y_i represents corresponding class values.

Step 3: The distance for a new data point is calculated.

$$d(x_{yangi}, x_i) = masofa(x_{yangi}, x_i)$$

Step 4: The K nearest neighbors are determined.

$$N_k = \{x_{i_1}, x_{i_2}, \dots, x_{i_k}\}$$

Step 5: The classification class is assigned, and the model value is computed.

$$y_{yangi} = M\{y_{i_1}, y_{i_2}, \dots, y_{i_k}\}$$

Step 6: End.

The developed K-NN algorithm is effective in performing intellectual analysis of economic indicators such as identifying sales delays, and it helps detect delays by considering various factors affecting sales delays.

III. Experimental Results

To assist in decision-making for identifying sales delays as economic indicators, the logistic regression-based machine learning algorithm was evaluated on an experimental dataset of sales data, and its results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Results of the Logistic Regression-based Machine Learning Algorithm.

Algorithm Name	Evaluation Metrics Results			
	Accur acy	Recall	Preci sion	F1 Score
Logistic Regression- based Algorithm	0,81	0,80	0,82	0,80

The Logistic Regression-based algorithm developed to assist in making decisions for identifying delays in sales as economic indicators achieved effective accuracy results.

Experimental studies were also conducted on the K-NN-based algorithm developed to assist in making decisions for identifying delays in sales as economic indicators, and the experimental results were presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Results of the Machine Learning Algorithm Based on the K-NN Method

Algorithm Name	Evaluation Metrics Results			
	Accura cy	Recall	Precisio n	F1 Score
Algorithm Based on the	0,83	0,85	0,84	0,84

K-NN Method				
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Experimental studies were conducted based on the developed decision tree algorithm for assisting decision-making in identifying sales delays as economic indicators, and the experimental results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Results of the machine learning algorithm based on the decision tree method.

Algorithm Name	Evaluation Metrics Results			
	Accur acy	Recall	Preci sion	F1 Score
Algorithm based on the decision tree method	0,89	0,90	0,88	0,89

Effective indicators were achieved based on the algorithm using the decision tree method.

The infographic of the experimental results is presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Performance indicators of machine learning-based algorithms.

The experimental results were carried out on algorithms based on machine learning methods such as Logistic Regression, K-NN, and Decision Tree. The experimental results show that the algorithm developed based on the Decision Tree method achieved the most effective performance.

IV. Conclusion

In this research work, a classification problem of artificial intelligence was solved to assist in decision-making for identifying delays in sales as

economic indicators. The classification problem of artificial intelligence was addressed using machine learning models. Logistic Regression, K-NN, and Decision Tree methods were selected as machine learning models. As a result, algorithms based on Logistic Regression, K-NN, and Decision Tree methods were developed, and the effectiveness indicators of the developed algorithms were analyzed.

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